

INFLUENCE OF TiO₂ ADDITION IN ALUMINUM ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

Aluminum alloys, especially the 2014 series, are widely used in the production of parts that require high heat resistance and hardness, for example, pistons for combustion engines.

The composites based on the aluminum alloy provide an increase in the high temperatures resistance. The addition of TiO₂ nanoparticles reinforcement demonstrates that the formation of precipitates is more evident where oxide particles are found. In order to avoid this agglomeration of precipitates it is necessary to promote a homogeneous dispersion of the reinforcement in the aluminum matrix composite [1].

The deformation that occurs during extrusion allows controlling the orientation and size of the grains, thus obtaining an increase in hardness by the oxides dispersion along the matrix, consequently improving the extruded material properties [2] [3].

This work verifies the influence of high-energy milling processing in the fabrication of an aluminum metal matrix composite reinforced with TiO₂ nanoparticles. The base alloy (AA2014) was produced by high-energy milling and subsequently the reinforcement was added. After obtaining the base alloy and the composite, the powders were compacted in a uniaxial cylindrical matrix with a compression tension of 490 MPa, and then the material was extruded at 490° C.

The morphology and size of the powders depends on the high energy milling process, that promotes constant fracture and welding during the process, forming the AA2014 alloy and the composite with 5% TiO₂.

Milling the base alloy in a high-energy mill for 10 h was sufficient for the powders to reach steady state. Figure 1 (a) represents the equiaxial morphology of the base alloy powder. With TiO₂ nanoparticles addition the particle morphology is changed, Figure 1 (b), composite powder with 5% TiO₂ presented equiaxial morphology. Figure 1 (c) shows a uniform distribution of the reinforcement nanoparticles, although clusters formation occurs, which can be observed in Figure 1 (d) for the same composite.

Figure 1 – Equiaxial morphology of base alloy, (a) after high-energy milling for 10h (b) Powder morphology of AA2014 + 5% TiO₂. (c) Reinforcement distribution in the matrix. (d) Clusters of TiO₂.

The addition of ceramic particles in a ductile alloy increases the fracture processes of the particles causing ductile particles deformation.

In AA2014 alloy occurs the formation of an incoherent composite with matrix, the CuAl₂ precipitate. Through transmission electron microscopy, it is possible to observe that TiO₂ is a nucleating region for the Cu precipitates formation. Figure 2 a) and b) shows the extruded base alloy microstructure with and without reinforcement. It is noticed that with the reinforcement addition the precipitates are smaller, indicating that TiO₂ slows the growth of precipitates.

The presence of TiO₂ is associated with a structure deformation in the interface matrix-reinforcement, enabling the nucleation of CuAl₂ precipitates in this region. Figure 2c) shows the GP zones, with thin disc-shaped blades form.

Figure 2 – Micrographs of (a) base alloy (b) composite (c) Transmission electron micrograph of 5% TiO₂ composite.

The materials produced by extrusion presented tensile strength values of 325 MPa for the base alloy and 362 MPa for the composite with 5% reinforcement.

The properties improvement of the composite compared to the base alloy, related to the tensile strength, are due to the hardening, the increase of the dislocations produced during the powders milling, and to the extrusion process, that allows the improvement of material's properties.

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